

FASTCAT-Edge Training & capacity building resources

Cos4Cloud Services

About the FASTCAT-Edge system and user guide

This is a system and user guide to [FASTCAT-Edge](#), a Cos4Cloud service that helps users build their own smart camera trap to record videos and pictures of wildlife activity which can be linked to a cloud-based service and help support identification of species names.

Description

FASTCAT-Edge is a service that helps users assemble a smart camera trap to record videos and pictures of wildlife activity and quickly identify the species names. Using Artificial Intelligence (AI) this service automatically filters out unwanted pictures from camera trap videos or images choosing only those of animals.

FASTCAT-Edge has been developed by [DynAlkon](#) as part of [Cos4Cloud](#), a European Horizon 2020 funded project. The Cos4Cloud project developed [thirteen services](#) boosting citizen science technological services to help increase and improve the quantity and quality of observations.

FASTCAT is a specification for Flexible Ai SysTEM for CAmera Traps, which supports two elements. **FASTCAT-Edge**, the service described in this guide, which helps users build and set up their own camera traps. The second is FASTCAT-Cloud, a cloud-based service (also developed by DynAlkon) that connects camera traps to a network that pools images as observations supporting identification.

Service Coordinator

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Cos4Cloud Coordinator

The following content has been provided to help guide users of this service.

WHAT IS FASTCAT-EDGE?

Flexible Ai SysTEm for CAmera Traps (FASTCAT) is a specification developed by DynAlkon and **FASTCAT-Edge** is an element of this services which helps users set up and use smart camera traps that record videos and pictures of wildlife activity in real time. Using Artificial Intelligence (AI) **FASTCAT-Edge** automatically identifies whether a scene contains an animal and filters out unwanted pictures to keep only the images wanted saving time deleting empty recordings or photos.

It can be linked to FASTCAT-Cloud, DynAlkon's cloud-based Cos4Cloud service, which connects camera traps to a network that pools images as observations that supports users to identify species in observations through AI. This system also connects with [iSpot](#) a citizen observatory focused on biodiversity, involved in Cos4Cloud which has integrated FASTCAT-Cloud as an AI-based species identification service.

FASTCAT-Edge works with [DynAlkonTrap](#), as a specification combining the necessary information about *Raspberry Pi*, the recommended hardware, and the open-source software to operate this targeted device.

WHO IS THIS SERVICE FOR AND WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS?

FASTCAT-Edge is aimed at those interested on recording wildlife and who might want to in build and set up a Do-It-Yourself (DIY) smart camera device to record videos and pictures of wildlife activity. It can help users to:

- Save time in selecting images i.e. to help estimate animal populations or study their behaviour.
- Capture thousands of animal photos and videos, including small or fast animals that are often missed with standard camera traps.
- Share wildlife images with citizen observatories, platforms or citizen science projects and help other researchers.
- Design observation project around the camera trap: **FASTCAT-Edge** acts as a general-purpose computer.

HOW DOES IT WORK?

FASTCAT-Edge integrates a system that can always record using some AI to decide when the camera trap needs to be triggered, capturing the best frames when needed. Innovative, the camera is always focused on looking for animals and once the system 'thinks' it has spotted an animal, it keeps the image. Other camera traps often miss the right frame by taking a much longer reaction time. For example, a lot of motion, does not necessarily mean an animal has passed by; it could be leaves falling from a tree. The idea is that this system can tell the difference.

An animal-detection machine-learning model integrated into the camera trap also detects small animals that are sometimes missed with standard commercial camera traps which require a minimum heat threshold to be triggered. This also can detect animals that move fast because there is almost no delay in the timeline from detecting a motion to the image being taken. **FASTCAT-Edge** supports the use of *Raspberry Pi*, which has the capabilities to execute the bespoke capture software and provide the smart functions.

Required hardware and software

The following hardware is needed to get started with **FASTCAT-Edge**:

- A *Raspberry Pi* Operating System (OS): Any model of the Raspberry Pi OS can be used; however, *Raspberry Pi Zero or Zero 2 W* are recommended as lower power consumption models.
- A *Raspberry Pi* Camera module: **FASTCAT-Edge** has been developed to support the [Raspberry Pi Camera Module](#) (There are others available, but these are unsupported however these could still work).
- A power supply for the *Raspberry Pi*
- Micro-SD card: a 64GB SD card is recommended to help support performance of the trap.
- A computer, tablet or mobile phone: this should be able to read and write to the selected micro SD card and is needed as the point of control for the *Raspberry Pi*.
- An ethernet cable (optional, if not using Wi-Fi).

See more here: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/preparing-the-raspberry-pi.html#necessary-hardware>

The following software tips will help with set up:

- DynAikonTrap is written to work on *Raspberry Pi OS (Legacy)*, this is the Raspberry Pi OS based on *Debian version 10 codename Buster*.
- Installing *Raspberry Pi OS Lite (Legacy)* is recommended which saves SD card space, reduces installation time and reduces load on the *Raspberry Pi* when running.
- On-going access to a computer with an SD card slot, is not required: once the SD card has been prepared, all remaining steps can be performed from any device that has a Secure Shell (SSH) client.

HOW TO USE FASTCAT-EDGE – A STEP BY STEP GUIDE

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INSTALL THE RASPBERRY PI OS AND SET UP THE SD CARD:

1.1 Insert the SD card into your computer*

- To get the system ready, for use first the SD card has to be prepared with the Raspberry Pi OS i.e. flashed (writing the software image file). See more here: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/preparing-the-raspberry-pi.html#imaging-tool>.
- The Raspberry Pi imaging tool is recommended and this requires downloading the operating system (Raspberry Pi OS Legacy, based on Debian Buster version 10) and copying the files to the SD card. See more here: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/preparing-the-raspberry-pi.html#flashing-the-sd-card>

* Please note: Installing the Raspberry Pi OS on the SD card will wipe all content therefore do ensure that any important data on the SD card has been backed up.

1.2 Set up the Raspberry Pi imaging tool:

From the welcome screen Click "Choose OS"

Then select *Raspberry Pi OS (other)*

Next select *Raspberry Pi OS Lite (Legacy)* and verify that it is “a port of Debian Buster”.

1.3 Configure the system:

Click the settings icon in the bottom right corner and fill in the details requested to configure the network and login details, as demonstrated in the example below:

- Set hostname*: this is what your Raspberry Pi will be called on your local network.
- Enable SSH: this allows logging into your Raspberry Pi over a network. Select “Use password authentication”.
- Set username* and password: these will be the credentials you will use to log into your Raspberry Pi.
- Configure wireless LAN: this is necessary for WiFi access for the Raspberry Pi.
- Set locale settings: set time zone and keyboard layout. It is important to set this correctly, so password entry will be correct on log in.

* Please note: although it is possible to use spaces in the hostname and username, it is not recommended to do so.

1.4 Select the SD card in the “storage” field.

Finally, click “write” to write the OS to the SD card.

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GETTING STARTED: ASSEMBLE THE CAMERA TRAP

Use the FASTCAT-Edge code and guide to set up your camera trap. See more here: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/preparing-the-raspberry-pi.html#installing-raspberry-pi-os>

2.1 Booting up for the first time

Insert the flashed SD card into your Raspberry Pi and connect the power supply. Your Pi should now start blinking, give it 5 minutes to boot up and initialise e for the first time. See more here: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/preparing-the-raspberry-pi.html#booting-for-the-first-time>

2.2 Using the SD card to expand the file system

For camera trapping usage the filesystem needs to be expanded to use all available space in the SD card. See how to do this here: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/preparing-the-raspberry-pi.html#expanding-the-filesystem>

2.3 Enabling the software and installing the camera

- Enable the camera module, see how to do this here: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/preparing-the-raspberry-pi.html#preparing-raspberry-pi-camera>. Installation depends on the type of Camera and Raspberry Pi. Here is a demonstration using the Raspberry Pi Zero W and the camera module: https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/_static/install-camera.webm.

- Test the camera and check the focus: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/preparing-the-raspberry-pi.html#installing-the-camera-hardware>

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RUN FASTCAT-EDGE USING DYNAIKON TRAP

DynAlkonTrap is the AI-enabled camera design, which combines all the necessary hardware and software, that has been developed to use the FASTCAT-Edge specification.

- Running the trap: this can be operated in two ways:
- Live-mode as an in-field Camera Trap or
- Emulated-mode i.e. previously captured video files to detect animals.

See set up information here: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/running-dynaikontrap.html>

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EXPORT IMAGES AND VIDEOS TO YOUR COMPUTER

Retrieve observations: Connect the camera trap to your PC, read files directly from the SD Card and retrieve observations and transfer images and videos, which will be automatically filtered (no need for additional software) and save files. See more here: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/running-dynaikontrap.html#retrieving-observations-from-the-camera-trap>

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CONFIGURE FASTCAT-CLOUD

FASTCAT-Edge can be integrated with FASTCAT-Cloud to upload species detected automatically using the available API. Configure the camera trap to do this by following instructions here: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/tuning.html>.

Other things the system can be set up to do:

- Check observations via the system log <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/web-viewer.html>
- The system is versatile and can be used in different locations etc. For tips on how to deploy i.e. with outdoor protection see: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/deploying-dynaikontrap.html>
- Filtering out empty images: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/pipelines/legacy.html>

INFORMATION AND FURTHER SUPPORT

Introduction to this Cos4Cloud service: <https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/services/fastcat-edge-camera-trap/>

Developer and other documentation: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/dev-docs.html>

Code repository: <https://gitlab.dynaikon.com/dynaikontrap>

Troubleshooting: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/web-viewer.html#troubleshooting>

DynAlkon Trap Wiki page: <https://dynaikon.com/trap/>

Tuning the Camera trap: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/tuning.html#tuning-the-trap>

DynAlkon Trap: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/>

User information: <https://dynaikon.com/trap-docs/fastcat-edge.html>

Video: What are FASTCAT-Edge and FASTCAT-Cloud: <https://youtu.be/vlCHgVIDu0A>

Article: DynAlkonTrap: Build your own artificial intelligence camera trap <https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/blog/dynaikontrap-artificial-intelligence-camera-trap-citizen-science-cos4cloud/>

Get the Cos4Cloud infographic for this service: [FASTCAT-Edge infographic](#)

Additional resources: [About the Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub](#)

This system and user guide is a training resource for FASTCAT-Edge, one of the technological services co-designed by the Cos4Cloud project (<https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/>). **Title: FASTCAT-Edge System and User Guide.** Service Coordinator DynAlkon. This guide is one of the Training and Capacity Building resources in the Cos4Cloud Toolbox & Evidence Hub developed by the Open University in collaboration with project partners. Contact: cos4cloud-toolbox@open.ac.uk.

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